

The power of MPC minutes: An empirical investigation into the value of central bank communication

Callum Ashworth
University of Bath - Economics
April 2024

Abstract

This dissertation investigates the informational value of qualitative central bank communication for future monetary policy decisions. We construct an indicator using natural language processing techniques that measures the sentiment of Bank of England (BoE) policy meeting minutes. Utilising an ordered probit model framework, we find strong evidence that the language used in the minutes can help to better predict the policy decision at the subsequent meeting. Our result is robust when controlling for an augmented Taylor rule, as well as different monetary policy environments. This finding supports the notion that communication is a key tool for policymakers with consistency between words and actions.

Table of Contents

Abstract	2
1. Introduction	4
2. Literature Review	6
3. Quantifying Bank of England communication	10
3.1 Communication source	10
3.2 Topic modelling	12
3.3 Dictionary	16
3.4 Communication indicator	17
4. Data	18
4.1 Dependent variable	18
4.2 Macroeconomic data controls	19
5. Empirical methodology	20
5.1 Theoretical background	20
5.2 Empirical model	21
6. Results	23
7. Robustness checks	26
7.1 Voting record	26
7.2 Alternative dictionaries	27
7.3 Unconventional monetary policy tools	27
8. Discussion and Policy Insights	29
9. Conclusion	31
Bibliography	33
Appendix	38

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my supervisor, Dr. Imran Shah for providing invaluable support and guidance throughout the entire process.

1. Introduction

Central bank communication has long been understood to be a significant channel in the transmission of monetary policy. It provides an opportunity for policymakers to express their view on the economy and give greater detail around policy decisions. Communication can influence agents' expectations for the future path of policy, which largely impacts the effectiveness of monetary policy transmission (Woodford, 2005). Expectations for the future will impact behaviour today, which emphasises the importance of understanding the value of qualitative communication. This phenomenon came to the forefront when central banks began to have their policy options limited in prolonged recessions. Interest rates were constrained by the effective lower bound, meaning central bankers considered the effectiveness of other tools – such as communication – to achieve their objective. In light of these developments, the importance of communication is well understood by policymakers:

“Monetary policy is 98% talk and only 2% action” ~ Bernanke (2015)

This emphasises the importance of communicating clearly to achieve price stability and manage expectations. One might argue that with clear communication, policy decisions should be more predictable as agents have greater knowledge of the decision-making process. This has been an area of increased focus as central banks have moved towards greater transparency (Blinder et al., 2008). Our study will focus on short-term expectations through examining the usefulness of central bank minutes for predicting subsequent decisions. Figure 1 highlights the role of communication in enhancing predictability. It makes a distinction between longer-term predictability with regards to credibility, and shorter-term aspects such as regular communication (Blattner et al., 2008). This highlights the importance of understanding the informational content of communication describing the current economic environment. Our study will shed light on the consistency between words and actions to help policymakers better understand the implications of publishing meeting minutes. It will focus on language describing the economic climate, which provides an indirect insight into future monetary policy.

Figure 1: The broader notion of monetary policy predictability. Source: Blattner et al. (2008, pp. 9)

The BoE’s Monetary Policy Committee (MPC) provides an interesting focal point for the impact of communication given their individualistic approach (Blinder, 2008). Different members of the committee express their differing views and the meeting minutes capture the dispersion of views on each policy decision. Researchers have extensively examined different forms of communication, albeit with difficulty given the qualitative nature. In the latest tightening cycle, the degree to which decisions are dependent on economic data releases has been in focus with communication emphasising the importance of specific releases (Bank of England, 2023b). We find that communication provides valuable information to help predict decisions, in addition to any signals extracted from data developments.

This dissertation makes original contributions to the literature by exploring how the language used to describe the balance of risks in the economy can be informative for future action by constructing a new indicator. This indicator uses natural language processing techniques to measure the hawkishness of the central bank’s language. We examine the predictive power of the indicator alongside macroeconomic data developments to assess the importance of the language used by central bankers. The results are compared to other measures, and we find evidence our indicator is a better fit for the data.

The structure of this paper is organised as follows: the relevant literature for both quantifying central bank communication and the empirical implications are outlined in

section 2. The construction process of our communicator indicator is described in section 3 and data is presented in section 4. The incorporation of the indicator into an empirical model is detailed in section 5. Section 6 presents the results for the empirical analysis and section 7 outlines various robustness checks. Section 8 discusses policy implications and section 9 gives our concluding remarks.

2. Literature Review

As central banks have become increasingly transparent, the literature on communication has grown rapidly, as documented by Blinder et al. (2008). The empirical work is divided into those that consider the impact of communication on predictability of future policy decisions, and those that analyse the creation of news for financial markets. These strands are interconnected given the weight of communication in future decisions will impact the extent to which it drives asset prices (Ehrmann & Fratzscher, 2007). Our study focuses on the former to explore the informational content included in qualitative communication.

The transmission of central bank communication through financial markets has been a longstanding area of inquiry in the literature. Romer and Romer (1989) first analysed the importance of the 'narrative approach' when looking at monetary disturbances. This illustrated that commentary around decisions can lead to real economy impacts, although emphasised the difficulty around measuring such a qualitative factor. Their paper paved the way for further research into the role of communication as an adequate tool for policymakers to shape expectations beyond conventional policies. Woodford (2005) emphasises the importance of communication when interest rates reach the effective lower bound to ensure effective monetary policy and improve the transmission.

Early studies examined the impact of communication events on financial market volatility. The release of these qualitative communication sources tends to coincide with monetary policy decisions and can provide additional information on policymakers' key considerations. Kohn and Sack (2003) control for the surprise component of the immediate interest rate decision and demonstrate that on days of FOMC statements, there is a higher amount of unexplained volatility in interest rate markets. Other studies have found similar results for the impact of communication on volatility across other advanced economies, including the UK (Connolly & Kohler, 2004; Reeves & Sawicki, 2007). This suggests communication moves market instruments, implying it contains economic news for financial markets. From a differing perspective, Coppel and

Connolly (2003) argue that aggregate volatility has subsided for many advanced economies at a similar rate as central banks have made information more publicly available. This relates to the idea that greater transparency can lower volatility due to a greater understanding of the monetary policy process. This general transition is widely accepted in the literature, although the rate at which volatility has reduced may differ based on the decision-making approach of the central bank. Ehrmann and Fratzscher (2007) find that the communication and decision-making strategy largely influences the degree of signal extraction for markets.

The limitation of much of the early literature focusing on financial market volatility around communication events is that it omits the directional intent of the policymaker (Blinder et al., 2008). The language used is carefully selected and can carry additional information to help readers understand the core considerations for monetary policy going forward. Thus, the effectiveness of communication to achieve the intended reaction is overlooked when analysing volatility.

Several studies look to measure the intended direction of the qualitative information conveyed by central bankers to improve understanding of these communication tools. Initially, Rosa and Verga (2007) pioneer a method to obtain a quantitative score for ECB president's introductory statements by manually classifying them on an ordered scale ranging from -2 (dovish) to +2 (hawkish).¹ These values indicate the stance of monetary policy with regards to the future path of interest rates. Furthermore, Ehrmann and Fratzscher (2007) divide communication into two distinct topic areas – monetary policy and economic outlook – using a similar manual approach. Such manual assignment methods present one way to construct a communication indicator, although great strides have been made in the empirical literature to reduce the degree of subjectiveness and improve repeatability. Therefore, recent innovations aim to utilise an automated classification method that appears less opaque.

The incorporation of basic natural language processing into the field of economics, with the development of specified dictionaries, has advanced the empirical work in quantifying central bank communication. Early examples in the literature include Dow, Klaes and Montagnoli (2009), who construct an index for policymaker uncertainty in the UK based on the frequency of the words 'uncertainty' and 'risk'. Whilst this

¹ A hawkish statement emphasises heightened inflationary pressure or a robust economic outlook - indicating higher interest rates. In contrast, dovish statements describe a dampened inflationary environment or a benign economic outlook - indicating lower interest rates.

approach is simplistic and fails to capture many of the nuances in communication, the results highlight the power of language. This instigated researchers to delve deeper into creating more detailed dictionaries. Apel and Grimaldi (2012) develop a list of field-specific words and nouns to classify the minutes of the Riksbank. This assesses word grouping as opposed to a single word to improve the accuracy of the indicator, and this dictionary has been tailored for other central banks (Apel, Grimaldi & Hull, 2022).

Using a different approach, Picault and Renault (2017) also use a dictionary to construct two separate indicators, although they use a term-weighting method which attaches weights to words based on their relative importance.² This helps to account for the priorities of central banks in achieving price stability. This approach to computational linguistics enables repeatable results and allows for international comparisons. Although, it must be considered that differences in dictionary specification can impact results, notably illustrated by Baranowski, Bennani and Doryń (2021). This highlights the importance of utilising a dictionary that is tailored to the specific institution. In support of these quantification methods, Lucca and Trebbi (2009) find more automated approaches provide more consistent results relative to manual classification approach. This methodology can mitigate the degree of ambiguity contained within these communication indicators.

The use of more advanced natural language processing techniques has gained momentum in the literature. This includes the use of generative probabilistic statistical models, also referred to as topic modelling. Blei, Ng and Jordan (2003) initially developed a method called Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) which has since been widely implemented in the field of economics. It encompasses a Bayesian topic modelling approach to natural language processing, whereby it analyses groupings of words that tend to appear together and assigns them to a topic. The probability a sentence belongs to a specified topic can then be extracted through identifying the number of words that are associated with a topic. Hansen and McMahon (2016) combine LDA analysis with the use of a dictionary to extract sentiment from the FOMC. In an extension of the approach for the UK, Hansen, McMahon and Tong (2019) construct a measure for the BoE Inflation Report to isolate the impact of uncertainty communication channels. We will follow a similar approach and combine topic modelling with dictionaries in order to construct a new indicator for BoE policy meeting minutes. It will incorporate elements of the Apel, Grimaldi and Hull (2022) dictionary

² Their indicator builds on the work of Ehrmann and Fratzscher (2007) by having one indicator for monetary policy (MP) and another for economic conditions (EC).

with various extensions to capture some idiosyncrasies in the BoE's communication choices. The literature of quantifying BoE minutes appears to be scarce in comparison to other central banks, and this study will shed light on these dynamics in the UK.

There is a consensus that central bank communication carries explanatory power for predicting policy decisions, albeit the extent and robustness of the relationship is debated. Gerlach-Kristen (2004) finds the voting record for the BoE carries valuable information for predicting future decisions. This considers the signal extracted from quantitative forms of communication and implies committee members' votes provide insight and can reveal when they believe the economy has reached a turning point. Focusing on sentiment conveyed by statements, studies highlight that ECB introductory statements and press conferences carry significant weight in helping to predict future monetary policy changes (Rosa & Verga, 2007). They find this information is complementary to macroeconomic data for numerous meetings ahead, although carries similar information as expectations from financial market measures. Similar results have been found for the ECB with respect to inter-meeting speech communication, suggesting it can carry explanatory power for decisions beyond the subsequent policy meeting (Bennani et al., 2020). Interestingly, Picault and Renault (2017) find their economic conditions indicator constructed from press conferences outperforms indicators made with other dictionaries, despite their monetary policy indicator being less informative. This further emphasises the importance of the dictionary used and suggests language around economic developments is sufficient to extract sentiment. We will focus on the language around key economic topics and compare the performance of our indicator to indicators created using the methodologies of other studies.

Contrastingly, Jansen and De Haan (2009) argue that the extent to which communication provides additional information for future ECB policy decisions to that contained in macroeconomic data is limited. It measures communication through headlines on financial newswire services and suggests models containing macroeconomic data perform similarly to those with communication indicators. This implies communication doesn't provide new information, but merely reiterates the information obtained from observing data. In this study, we will consider official meeting minutes to remove any noise included in newswire headlines and will control for key macroeconomic data releases, such as CPI inflation and Industrial Production.

Various studies that examine the directional intent of communication assess financial market's reaction to the publication. Initially, Ehrmann and Fratzscher (2007) find using

an EGARCH model that movement in short-term interest rates can be explained by the directional intent of communication related to future monetary policy. The authors analyse the reaction to inter-meeting communication and suggest BoE speeches generate a smaller reaction than other central banks due to their collegial communication strategy and dispersed voting patterns. In recent years, the committee's communication style has perhaps become more individualistic, and our study will explore the degree of predictability for the BoE. Using a different approach, Rosa and Verga (2007) instead attempt to isolate the exogenous component of communication, and similarly show using an event study that central bank rhetoric can help to explain movements in interest rate derivatives. This is intuitive as interest rate swaps capture expectations for future monetary policy and the use of words suggesting there may be further changes factors into market prices. The movement of markets around communication events can spill into other asset classes such as equities (Rosa, 2011). Thus, communication can impact market instruments due to implications for future asset prices, although our study will focus on the degree of predictability without looking at market reactions.

3. Quantifying Bank of England communication

This section outlines the text data sources examined and provides a detailed explanation for the construction of our communication indicator, which combines natural language processing techniques with a central bank specific dictionary.

3.1 Communication source

To analyse the informational content of qualitative communication, the release that carries most importance to spectators should be utilised as a data source. This study uses the monetary policy meeting minutes given it provides a detailed description of the key considerations at the time of each meeting. Dow, Klaes and Montagnoli (2009) argue minutes give the most clearly articulated description of the rationale behind BoE policy decisions. Through capturing the factors driving the latest interest rate decision, it provides a lucrative source of information to gain insight into the reaction function of policymakers (i.e. what their policy action is responding to in the economy). Financial market participants identify consistent well-written minutes to be related to the perceived ability of the central bank to communicate effectively (Hayo & Neuenkirch, 2015). Furthermore, the use of minutes releases has been widely adopted in the literature as more central banks have made these documents publicly available (Apel & Grimaldi, 2012; Tadle, 2021). Thus, we focus on the minutes releases to gauge the sentiment of the committee.

The policy horizon of interest is from 2008-2023. This captures both tightening and loosening monetary policy cycles, which will help understand the dynamics of the BoE's communication and identify the words that are commonly associated together. Our study analyses 163 officially scheduled minutes releases that span the relevant period. As discussed later, due to constraints around the availability of macroeconomic data, the empirical analysis focuses on the period 2009-2023. This captures interest rate cuts for the latter part of the Great Financial Crisis. Across our horizon, the meeting frequency changed from monthly to 6-weekly in 2016. In addition, the minutes were released in the weeks following the policy decision prior to August 2015, and on the same day as the policy decision after this point. Beyond this point, a summary of the meeting outcome is included at the start of the minutes, and this is included in our analysis. Figure 2 outlines the two release schedules included in our time horizon.

Figure 2: Timeline of release schedule

Having selected an information source to analyse, there are various steps required to ensure the data is in a suitable format for textual analysis³. Initially, all minutes documents are loaded into a data frame with each observation representing an individual minutes release. All pages that provide no relevant economic information are stripped to ensure only the monetary policy summary and meeting minutes remain.⁴ For our analysis, we convert the text into tokens, which represents a specified grouping of

³ All textual analysis is conducted using R Studio.

⁴ The summary gives a brief description of the key developments driving the decision and the minutes provide a detailed account of all discussions throughout the process.

sentences. Subsequently, various steps follow for the ease of computational linguistic analysis. Wecken and Büchsenmann (2019) highlight the systematic process of cleaning text data in a step-by-step manner, which is largely outlined in Figure 3, with an additional step of reducing all words to their simplest form using a stemming algorithm.

Firstly, all words are converted to lower case to standardise the structure. This will ensure that when the frequency of words is calculated, capital letters will not classify the same word under different categories. Subsequently, all punctuation, symbols and numbers are removed as they are not the focus of our analysis. English stop words are removed to improve accuracy as they are frequently used without providing informational content. An example would be the removal of connecting words such as ‘the’ as this has no implications for the view of the committee. This prevents the topic analysis from being congested and allows us to focus on words describing the economy. After we have removed all stop words, we strip the additional whitespace where these words were originally located. Finally, a stemming algorithm is applied to reduce all words to their simplest form and ensure we capture all versions of the same word. This means all words that come from the same root word are standardised and grouped together, which ensures our natural language processing technique identifies the foundational meaning of all words. For example, both ‘decline’ and ‘declining’ will stem to ‘declin’ and this simplifies the process of counting key words in our unsupervised processing framework. This is a common feature in much of the textual analysis literature where we utilise the stemming algorithm developed by Porter (1980).

Figure 3: Text cleaning process

3.2 Topic modelling

When extracting a quantitative signal from qualitative central bank communication, manual classification and the use of defined dictionaries appear to be the most prominent in the literature. In this dissertation, we combine the dictionary approach with topic modelling (LDA) to improve the accuracy when counting descriptive words, similar to the approach of Hansen and McMahon (2016). Initially, topic modelling

provides an automated approach to group words that are commonly used together. The key inputs into an LDA model are the text data and number of topics (ibid, 2016). The former input is a corpus containing all sentences from the BoE minutes between 2008-2023. This involves constructing a Document-Term-Matrix grouped at sentence level. The contents of the matrix specify the frequency of all unique words contained within each sentence. Across our horizon, the inputs include 30578 sentences consisting of 3573 unique words. Hansen, McMahon and Prat (2017) highlight an advantage of using LDA is that it reduces dimensionality of the data in a probabilistic manner. This simplifies the issue by reducing the plethora of potential groupings into a smaller number of distinct topics.

The number of topics must be manually specified for the probabilistic model to determine the allocation of words to a predetermined number of topics. Each topic will be characterised by a distribution of words. In this study, we identify the optimal number of topics with the aid of two measures that consider the coherence, perplexity and stability of models with different topic numbers. The selection of the optimal number of topics must consider the trade-off between the ability of a model to accurately predict the classification of an additional section of text, referred to as perplexity in the literature, and the degree of interpretability (Chang et al., 2009). Figure 4 highlights these measures, with each having a different criterion. Initially, we consider an indicator that utilises a density approach to optimise similarity between words contained within a topic and minimise coherence between words across different topics (Cao et al., 2009). This is denoted CaoJuan2009, and a lower value of this measure is optimal for maximum similarity within topics and minimal crossover amongst different topics. Furthermore, we consider an indicator that solely focuses on maximising the divergence between different topics (Deveaud, Sanjuan & Bellot, 2014). Contrastingly, a higher value of this indicator is optimal as it implies less similarity between words in different topics (denoted Deveaud2014 in Figure 4).

It is evident that both metrics favour a larger number of topics. The top indicator (CaoJuan2009) illustrates a trend towards zero, whilst the second indicator (Deveaud2014) converges towards one. This suggests increasing the number of topics improves the coherence of words within topics and leads to a greater divergence of distinct topics. This is intuitive as when analysing central bank communication, greater granularity will improve the separation of topics that can be referred to in different contexts. Whilst more topics improves coherence of topics and divergence of different groupings, we must consider the interpretability of the model in a heuristic manner.

Therefore, we have decided to use 14 topics for our model. At this point, both metrics present sufficient evidence to support this selection with the rate of change plateauing in the convergence towards an optimal number of topics. Our topic specification enables interpretation with ease and strikes a balance between interpretability and coherence. This is largely consistent with Hansen and McMahon (2016), who specify a model with 15 topics. This seeks to ensure words in the same topic are related and there is minimal overlap between words of different topics.

Figure 4: Topic selection for LDA model

Subsequently, we can run our LDA model and obtain topics that are identified through analysing statistical patterns. These topics can be assessed by inspecting the most probable words associated with each latent field. Figure 5 shows a visualisation for topics that are deemed to clearly represent an overarching economic topic, whereby the words outlined have been extracted from the posterior distribution of words related to each topic. More simply, it shows the top 50 words that are most likely associated with each topic highlighted. For example, the top words associated with topic 1 evidently relate to economic growth, with the most probable words including growth, GDP and demand. Constructing these topics provides an automated method to group sentences and helps to overcome many of the issues that stem from a sole dictionary method, such as word crossover for different economic topics (Hansen, McMahon & Prat, 2017). An example would be that ‘slack’ may be used to describe the labour market or more generally economic activity, and a dictionary will be unable distinguish between both cases. Therefore, LDA provides a clear approach to separate different topics and accurately extract sentiment for our selected topics outlined in Figure 5.

The posterior distribution of topics for each document can be calculated and used to assign a topic to individual sentences. This assignment considers the latent variable that explains the greatest proportion of the sentence. Subsequently, these sentences can be divided by topic, and we can use a dictionary to identify descriptive words that have a policy inclination for each topic.

3.3 Dictionary

This dissertation builds on an existing dictionary to examine the hawkish and dovish modifier words used to describe an economic topic. We extend the dictionary of Apel, Grimaldi and Hull (2022), which has been adopted throughout the literature (Bennani & Neuenkirch, 2016; Hubert & Labondance, 2021). These studies assess communication across different central banks, emphasising the robustness of the dictionary to capture the sentiment of different communication styles. In our analysis, additional features are added to the dictionary to measure BoE communication more accurately. This includes adding topics such as wage growth, given committee members frequently emphasise its importance (Haskel, 2024). Furthermore, the inclusion of this factor is motivated by the survey responses from financial market participants (Figure 6). This data comes from the BoE's Market Participants Survey and highlights the significant perceived weight of wage growth data driving future monetary policy decisions in the recent tightening cycle (c. 25% weighting). Since the perceived importance is likely to stem from emphasis in communication, we include wage growth as a topic in our analysis to improve the accuracy of our measure. This broadens the criteria related to communication channels, allowing us extract sentiment from a greater portion of the BoE minutes.

In addition, the list of modifier words is expanded for some topics to capture sentiment from words frequently used by the BoE. An example is the addition of the word 'disappoint' to the dictionary for economic growth. If this were not included, there would be 22 sentences throughout our sample that would not be counted, despite having a dovish connotation. Further topics and descriptive words are included in our measure, where the full dictionary can be found in Appendix A1.

Figure 6: Factor weightings by market participants for the prospect of further interest rate hikes. Data source: Bank of England (2023a)

The data is assessed on a per sentence basis before aggregating across documents. We count the number of sentences that include either a hawkish or dovish term with respect to the assigned topic. When a sentence contains both a hawkish and dovish term, it is removed from our analysis. Appendix A2 highlights a few examples of how the classification process works, outlining two statements that would be classified as hawkish and dovish respectively, alongside a statement that provides no policy inclination. A further precautionary measure is taken for topic 8, where all sentences including the word ‘unemployment’ are filtered into a different data frame due to the opposite meaning of descriptive words associated to employment versus unemployment.

3.4 Communication indicator

The sentence scores are aggregated by summing all sentences within a document that have been identified as either hawkish or dovish. Following Apel, Grimaldi and Hull (2022), the net inclination measure is calculated using formula (1) which takes the difference between hawkish and dovish sentences over the total sum of sentences that give a policy inclination.⁵ Figure 7 plots our indicator and a smoothed curve highlighting the average of local points with a confidence interval. We can see that the movement is largely in line with expectations around fluctuations in economic activity. At times of recession the sentiment appears more dovish, whilst the more recent inflationary surge throughout 2021 is characterised by a local peak in the indicator.

⁵ This implies our indicator will always be bound between -1 and +1.

$$Indicator_t = \frac{\sum hawkish\ statements_t - \sum dovish\ statements_t}{\sum hawkish\ statements_t + \sum dovish\ statements_t} \quad (1)$$

Figure 7 - Communication indicator

4. Data

4.1 Dependent variable

Over the years, interest rates have been the main monetary policy instrument of central banks and adjustments have been infrequent and in discrete increments (Vanderhart, 2000). This applies to the sample period for our empirical analysis (2009-2023) with policy being unchanged for 130 meetings, and of those meetings where a change occurred, around 43% were by an increment of 25 basis points. Figure 8 highlights the distribution of interest rate decisions with most observations contained within a narrow range. Thus, for our baseline analysis, we construct a policy variable that indicates whether the BoE tightens, loosens, or leaves the policy rate unchanged, and this follows a natural ordering.

$$\Delta i_t = \begin{cases} 3 \rightarrow \text{tightening policy} \\ 2 \rightarrow \text{policy unchanged} \\ 1 \rightarrow \text{easing policy} \end{cases}$$

This ordinal categorisation helps to overcome an obvious limitation associated with considering the size of policy rate changes, whereby this would reduce the number of observations in certain categories and limit the validity of the model (Baranowski, Bennani & Doryń, 2021). These three discrete categories capture the direction of an interest rate change and are sufficient to gauge the policy stance. Whilst it could be

argued that unconventional policy tools have become increasingly prevalent, changes in the policy rate remain sufficient for our study with MPC members emphasising Bank Rate to be the active monetary policy tool (Ramsden, 2023). Nonetheless, we consider a dependent variable with unconventional policy tools included in the robustness section.

Figure 8: Distribution of interest rate decisions

4.2 Macroeconomic data controls

For our study, various macroeconomic data releases are examined given they may provide information to policymakers on the state of the economy. Central bankers across advanced economies have emphasised the importance of following data developments in times of elevated uncertainty (Schnabel, 2023). Initially, for inflation data we use the headline CPI inflation rate. This differs to the inflation measure used by Picault and Renault (2017) as they consider the ECB's prominent measure, whereas CPI aligns with the BoE's official inflation target. Thus, it accurately captures inflation developments of core importance to the BoE. Financial markets sensitivity to this indicator highlights the perceived importance for the central bank's reaction function (please see Appendix A3 for event study analysis). Furthermore, for a measure on economic activity we use seasonally adjusted Industrial Output data from Refinitiv at monthly frequency. It measures the economic activity across core production sectors for the UK and acts as a good proxy for output. Orphanides (2001) stresses the importance of incorporating data developments available to policymakers at the time of each meeting, thus first release data between meetings is used for our analysis. This aims to accurately approximate the information set available to the MPC without adjusting for any revisions that occur later. Due to constraints on the availability of first

release CPI figures and release dates, we are only able to obtain this data since the latter part of 2008.

5. Empirical methodology

5.1 Theoretical background

As discussed, our dependent variable follows a natural ordering with discrete jumps between policy categories. When considering a model framework, a linear regression model will not be appropriate to capture the relationship as these methods implicitly assume the distance between categories is the same (Daykin & Moffatt, 2002). Changes in monetary policy may not be symmetric, and with the bulk of decisions leaving interest rates unchanged, the relationship is likely to be non-linear for extremely hawkish/dovish communication. Therefore, our analysis employs an ordered probit model to analyse the relationship between communication and subsequent policy action. This approach will capture the probability of falling within an ordinal category (Asteriou & Hall, 2021). This approach is consistent with methodology in much of the recent literature assessing the predictability of monetary policy decisions (Apel & Grimaldi, 2012; Jung, 2016).

The ordered probit model estimates coefficients and threshold points to capture the relationship between our ordinal policy variable and a set of explanatory variables. These threshold points represent the boundaries for the underlying latent variable, to which the probability of the outcome is estimated under the cumulative normal distribution (Daykin & Moffatt, 2002). Greene (2020) outlines the model dynamics where y^* is the unobserved latent variable, in our case Bank Rate, and δ_i is the respective cut-points that divide the density function for our three discrete outcomes:

$$y^* = \mathbf{x}'\boldsymbol{\beta} + \varepsilon \quad \text{where } \varepsilon \sim N(0,1)$$

$$y = 1 \text{ if } y^* \leq \delta_1$$

$$y = 2 \text{ if } \delta_1 \leq y^* \leq \delta_2$$

$$y = 3 \text{ if } \delta_2 \leq y^*$$

The probability of the dependent variable being in one of the respective categories is depicted below, whereby Φ denotes the cumulative density function (ibid, 2020). The ordered probit model employs maximum likelihood estimation to derive model estimates, which follows an iterative process to return estimates with the greatest likelihood.

$$Pr(y = 1 | \mathbf{x}) = \Phi(\delta_1 - \mathbf{x}'\boldsymbol{\beta})$$

$$Pr(y = 2 | \mathbf{x}) = \Phi(\delta_2 - \mathbf{x}'\boldsymbol{\beta}) - \Phi(\delta_1 - \mathbf{x}'\boldsymbol{\beta})$$

$$Pr(y = 3 | \mathbf{x}) = 1 - \Phi(\delta_2 - \mathbf{x}'\boldsymbol{\beta})$$

5.2 Empirical model

The baseline specification for our ordered probit model is depicted below:

$$\Delta i_{t+1} = a_1 \Delta i_t + a_2 \Delta(\pi_t - \pi_t^*) + a_3 communication_t + a_4 \Delta(y_t - y_t^*) + \varepsilon_{t+1}$$

Where Δi_t represents the policy stance at the last monetary policy meeting to control for persistence. Moreover, $\Delta(\pi_t - \pi_t^*)$ and $\Delta(y_t - y_t^*)$ represent the change in the deviations of inflation and output from trend between the current and previous meetings respectively. Finally, $communication_t$ represents the level of our communication variable at the last meeting. ε_{t+1} denotes the error term.

Initially, the inclusion of our communication indicator intends to capture the indirect effect of language describing the balance of economic risks for future monetary policy. We expect a positive relationship between hawkish communication and subsequent policy action due to the forward-looking nature of monetary policy.⁶ Our model also incorporates a lagged version of the dependent variable. This captures the previous policy decisions and potential feedback effects of monetary policy in practice. Bonciani and Oh (2023) emphasise the importance of an autoregressive component when modelling monetary policy due to interest rate smoothing being optimal through different stages in business cycles. This encompasses a gradual change in the policy stance of a central bank being preferable to achieve its objective.

Our model includes various controls alongside our communication indicator to prevent omitted variable bias from impacting our results. The incorporation of data releases in the decision-making process is clearly outlined by Taylor (1993), whereby a rule is proposed for central banks to implement optimal monetary policy based on data developments between policy meetings. Therefore, we extend our model to control for an augmented Taylor rule to capture these considerations for key indicators, such as inflation and output.

For inflation we consider the change in the gap between CPI inflation and the 2% inflation target for the UK. Considering the distance of inflation from trend captures the differing degree of policy intervention when the inflation deviates further from the specified target. It is expected that the MPC would respond more forcefully with their decision when inflation substantially departs from the target to ensure expectations of

⁶ Appendix A4 plots the value of our communication indicator from the last meeting against the policy variable.

the public remain anchored. Assuming the BoE is credible in achieving their inflation target, agents will be expecting inflation to converge back to target. In addition, the model includes the output gap measure, where the distance from trend output is considered. Given there is no official target for output, the trend series is calculated using a Hodrick-Prescott (HP) filter. This separates the time series into a cyclical and trend component with a smoothing parameter lambda to penalise variability in the trend (Hodrick & Prescott, 1997). This method is chosen for our analysis due to its widespread use throughout macroeconomic literature (De Jong & Sakarya, 2016). We set lambda to 14400, consistent with the literature when using data at a monthly frequency (Sauer & Sturm, 2007).

For the use of an ordinal regression model to be valid, the proportional odds assumption must hold (Brant, 1990). This means the odds of moving to a higher category is consistent for each considered outcome. We run various diagnostic tests to justify the use of our ordinal choice model and ensure the assumption holds for the data. The results of these tests are reported for our baseline specification in Table 1, with all tests finding no evidence that the proportional odds assumption is violated. Liu et al. (2023) argue that the Brant and Wolfe-Gould tests produce the most reliable results for all sample sizes. Therefore, we focus on these tests where both have the null hypothesis that the proportional odds assumption holds. Both have p-values of 0.501 and 0.505 respectively, meaning we cannot reject the null hypothesis that the data is consistent with proportional odds, and we proceed with the use of an ordered probit model.⁷

Table 1: Parallel lines assumption diagnostic tests

Test	χ^2	Degrees of freedom	$P > \chi^2$
Wolfe-Gould	3.324	4	0.505
Brant	3.353	4	0.501
Score	3.654	4	0.455
Likelihood ratio	3.324	4	0.505
Wald	3.338	4	0.503

⁷ Whilst stationarity is not strictly required in discrete choice models, researchers often assume it holds for statistical simplicity (Regenwetter & Davis-Stober, 2017). Appendix A5 provides a summary table, including results from an ADF test that highlight we can assume all series are trend stationary.

6. Results

In this section, results of the impact of our communication indicator on the predictability of future monetary policy are presented. Table 2 presents these results when controlling for macroeconomic data. Column (1) solely considers the macroeconomic data releases for inflation and production. In column (2), the communication indicator is introduced whilst controlling for inflation data. The final column (3) includes our communication measure and both macroeconomic data controls.⁸ The interpretation of coefficients differs to a standard linear model, as they measure the change in the cumulative normal probability of the policy variable falling in a categorical outcome for a unit change in the independent variable (Apel & Grimaldi, 2012). This can complicate interpretations and we therefore report the average marginal effects (AME) for our communication indicator to simplify interpretation. For our analysis, this considers the change in the probability of an interest rate rise based on a unit increase in value of the communication measure, as depicted by the derivative below.

$$\frac{\partial Pr(y = 3 | \mathbf{x})}{\partial x_i} = \Phi(\mathbf{x}'\boldsymbol{\beta} - \delta_2)\beta_i$$

As expected, previous policy decisions have a positive association with future monetary policy decisions and this result is statistically significant at the 1% level for all model specifications. This is consistent with the findings for other advanced economies (Picault & Renault, 2017). Intuitively, this highlights a gradual approach to implementing monetary policy, with past decisions influencing future decisions. Cobham (2003) argues the predominant reason for interest rate smoothing in the UK is the serial correlation of shocks that warrant a central bank response. Whilst the persistence of exogenous economic shocks is a key factor, other reasons such as elevated uncertainty and the prolonged period of rates hovering around the effective lower bound may play a significant role in our result.

Furthermore, we find CPI inflation has a positive and statistically significant coefficient for each specification. This is intuitive as when inflation is elevated above target, one would expect the central bank has a higher likelihood of raising interest rates at the next meeting to combat inflationary pressures. Interest rates are their main policy instrument

⁸ We report the results obtained from an ordered logit model in Appendix A6. This is another ordinal regression model that assumes the latent variable follows a logistic distribution, which is expected to provide similar results given both densities are similar (Brooks, 2019). The results obtained paint a similar picture to our ordered probit model.

to achieve stable inflation and this result is largely in line with much of the literature (Picault & Renault, 2017). We find the coefficient on our production measure, acting as a proxy for economic activity, is statistically insignificant and small in magnitude. This suggests real time developments in industrial production are not helpful for predicting policy decisions (Sauer & Sturm, 2007). The result implies the BoE is less responsive to developments in economic activity than inflation. A potential explanation is linked to the flattening in the Phillips curve observed in recent decades, as documented by Blanchard et al. (2015).⁹ When inflation is less sensitive to fluctuations in output, central bankers may be less inclined to engage in monetary policy to influence economic activity (Kuttner & Robinson, 2010). This may be further exacerbated in the UK given the BoE has a primary inflation objective which differs to other central banks that have a dual mandate. In addition, our stylised macroeconomic control variables are not exhaustive and central banks will likely consider a wider range of data developments (Sturm & De Haan, 2010).

Finally, the communication indicator has a positive coefficient, which is significant at the 1% level when controlling for both inflation and output releases in model (3), as well as when relaxing the output control in model (2). The marginal effects presented suggest that a one unit increase in the communication indicator implies the probability of an interest rate rise at the next meeting increases by approximately 11.3%, when holding all other variables at their sample mean. This result is consistent with the findings for other central banks that minutes provide additional information to help predict future decisions (Hayo & Neuenkirch, 2010; Apel & Grimaldi, 2012). Minutes capture the view on the balance of risks around economic developments, which plays a significant role in monetary policy decision-making. The model including the communication indicator has a higher Pseudo R^2 relative to the model with only macroeconomic data (0.576 compared to 0.542 without the communication indicator). This measure relates to how well the model fits the data, whereby it rises as the log-likelihood of the probit function increases relative to a restricted model with no predictors (Brooks, 2019). The higher log-likelihood further supports the better fit of the model for predicting the observed decisions. Such findings potentially contrast with the results of Ehrmann and Fratzscher (2007), who suggest that BoE decisions are less predictable. Whilst we have not considered an international comparison, the results provide evidence that information is available to help spectators anticipate decisions and our indicator may further enhance the degree of predictability.

⁹ This refers to the relationship between inflation and output.

Table 2: Ordered probit model regression results

	Policy decision (Δi_{t+1})		
	(1)	(2)	(3)
Δi_t	2.775*** (0.352)	2.603*** (0.367)	2.625*** (0.371)
$\Delta(\pi_t - \pi_t^*)$	0.707** (0.318)	0.653** (0.310)	0.675** (0.312)
$\Delta(y_t - y_t^*)$	-0.019 (0.017)		-0.024 (0.020)
$communication_t$		1.420*** (0.473)	1.435*** (0.473)
Cut-off coefficients			
δ_1	3.212*** (0.633)	2.582*** (0.698)	2.633*** (0.701)
δ_2	7.548*** (0.828)	7.353*** (0.854)	7.399*** (0.865)
Marginal effects			
ME_3		0.113* (0.060)	0.113* (0.059)
Observations	153	153	153
Pseudo R ²	0.542	0.574	0.576
Log-Likelihood	-34.746	-32.319	-32.169
AIC	0.520	0.489	0.499

Notes: Huber-White standard errors are reported in parenthesis for coefficient estimates to account for potential heteroskedasticity, where *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$ and * $p < 0.1$. ME_3 denotes the marginal effect of a unit increase in the communication indicator on the probability of an interest rate rise at the next policy meeting (other independent variables held at their sample average).

Table 3 outlines the summary statistics for our ordered probit model's predictions, whereby the prediction is defined as the ordinal outcome with the highest probability of occurring for model (3). It is apparent that our model accurately predicts future interest rate decisions with a large proportion of decisions correctly anticipated. On aggregate, the model correctly predicts 93% of the realised policy changes within our sample period. The proportion of interest rate cuts correctly predicted is marginally lower, perhaps reflecting the unique environments in which this monetary easing took place. Initially, our sample spans the latter part of the great financial crisis policy intervention. Apel, Grimaldi and Hull (2022) highlight the importance of tailoring a model to control for housing market developments to accurately predict this period. We haven't included housing specific controls, and this may partially reflect the worse performance in predicting expansionary monetary policy. In addition, policymakers have emphasised the unique nature of the interest rate cut in response to the decline in the exchange rate following Brexit (Broadbent, 2017). The unprecedented nature of this exogenous shock makes it difficult to predict from prior communication and data releases.

Table 3: Prediction evaluation

Policy decision	Observations	Correct (%)	Incorrect (%)
1	6	67	33
2	131	96	4
3	16	81	19
Total	153	93	7

7. Robustness checks

Our results remain robust to tweaks in the baseline model specification. This is the case when using different quantitative communication factors, when considering other methods for quantifying language, as well as when a broader definition of monetary policy is used as the dependent variable. In all cases, we keep the control for CPI inflation.

7.1 Voting record

Initially, it could be argued that the quantitative signal extracted from the votes of committee members, which is released alongside the minutes, provides the greatest assistance in predicting future policy decisions. This provides a leading insight into individual policymaker's view for the direction of monetary policy. We estimate the model with a lagged variable that captures the dispersion of voting at the previous meeting. The calculation of the dispersion largely follows the literature looking at the difference between the average vote of all MPC members and the consensus decision (Gerlach-Kristen, 2004). A positive value indicates the distribution of votes is skewed towards a higher level of interest rates than is announced (vice versa). The equation is highlighted below:

$$dispersion_t = average(i_{jt}) - i_t$$

In line with El-Shagi and Jung (2015), the positive coefficient on the dispersion measure suggests the voting record for the MPC can help to predict future decisions. This is consistent with our prior expectation that committee members deviating from consensus can reflect their view on the economy, especially at the start and end of policy cycles. However, the coefficient is only significant at the 10% level. In addition, the magnitude of the coefficient is relatively small which suggests our communication indicator may provide more information around subsequent policy decisions.

7.2 Alternative dictionaries

As previously discussed, the method used to extract a quantitative score from communication can impact results. Therefore, we compare the results for our indicator to those obtained from using other dictionaries without utilising topic modelling techniques. This is a common feature in several studies to ensure an indicator aligns with dictionaries well established in the literature (Gardner, Scotti & Vega, 2021). Firstly, we consider a more general dictionary tailored for financial reporting language (Loughran & McDonald, 2011), which will be denoted as LM. This provides a broad range of positive and negative words to be used as an input into sentiment analysis. Furthermore, a lexicon tailored for central bank communication by the ECB is used to assess the minutes (Picault & Renault, 2017). In contrast to the other dictionary, this computes scores for both monetary policy (MP) and economic conditions (EC), as well as weighting words based on their perceived importance. We only consider the EC indicator given this has a direct comparison to our analysis (denoted as PR). For all communication related indicators in Table 4, we compute the standardised version to allow direct comparison as highlighted below.

$$\textit{standardised index}_t = \frac{x_t - \bar{x}}{\sigma_x}$$

Initially, the sign observed for all communication indicators is positive, suggesting central bank communication that is deemed hawkish or positive about the economic outlook is associated with a higher probability of future interest rate increases. This further supports our results that BoE minutes are helpful for predicting future decisions regardless of the method used to quantify them, consistent with findings for the ECB (Sturm & De Haan, 2010). Our results suggest both the LM and PR indicators appear to be reasonably good at capturing the sentiment conveyed by policymakers. Nonetheless, our indicator suggests the largest effect of communication and to the highest level of significance (1%). A one standard deviation increase in the communication indicator implies the probability of an interest rate rise at the next meeting increases by 3.6%. This emphasises the importance of communication and the higher Pseudo R^2 potentially reflects the greater degree of accuracy for our indicator.

7.3 Unconventional monetary policy tools

To ensure our communication indicator provides valuable information in different policy environments, we consider a broader definition of monetary policy for our dependent variable. Quantitative easing (QE) is an unconventional policy tool that aims to stimulate economic activity when interest rates are near zero by increasing the size

of the central bank's balance sheet (Bernanke & Reinhart, 2004). Largely following the methodology of Apel, Grimaldi and Hull (2022), we can incorporate this policy tool into our framework by having our dependent variable equal to 1 when the BoE announces QE purchases, as well as when interest rates are lowered (denoted as Δi_{t+1}^{QE}). We identify these announcements in line with Froemel, Joyce and Kaminska (2022).¹⁰ Out of the 13 QE announcements we have identified, there are 9 additional cases where our dependent variable is equal to 1 compared to the standard measure in our baseline specification.

In line with previous findings, the coefficient on our communication indicator remains positive in column (5), albeit at a lower level of statistical significance (5%). Similarly, the marginal effect is identical with a one standard deviation increase in our indicator increasing the probability of contractionary monetary policy at the next meeting by 3.6% higher. This suggests communication can be informative for predicting unconventional policy action, consistent with the findings of Apel, Grimaldi and Hull (2022). Although, the substantially lower log-likelihood of -69.7 implies the model is a worse fit for the data. The inclusion of unconventional policies appears to increase difficulty of predicting policy, perhaps reflecting the elevated uncertainty that remains around these tools (Bernanke, Reinhart & Sack, 2004).

¹⁰ Appendix A7 outlines the dates of each announcement.

Table 4: Robustness checks for ordered probit model regression

	Policy decision				
	Δi_{t+1}	Δi_{t+1}	Δi_{t+1}	Δi_{t+1}	Δi_{t+1}^{QE}
Δi_t^{QE}					1.505*** (0.269)
Δi_t	2.603*** (0.367)	2.644*** (0.355)	2.592*** (0.369)	2.948*** (0.363)	
$\Delta(\pi_t - \pi_t^*)$	0.653** (0.310)	0.630* (0.335)	0.674* (0.347)	0.703** (0.352)	0.516* (0.308)
$communication_t$	0.447*** (0.149)				0.293** (0.134)
PR_t^{EC}			0.335* (0.186)		
LM_t		0.249* (0.146)			
$dispersion_t$				0.074* (0.038)	
QE	No	No	No	No	Yes
Cut-off coefficients					
δ_1	2.582*** (0.699)	2.805*** (0.672)	2.700*** (0.717)	3.434*** (0.704)	1.340*** (0.513)
δ_2	7.353*** (0.855)	7.311*** (0.827)	7.269*** (0.832)	7.997*** (0.812)	4.701*** (0.587)
Marginal effects					
ME_3	0.036* (0.019)	0.021 (0.016)	0.025 (0.015)		0.036** (0.018)
Observations	153	153	153	153	153
Pseudo R ²	0.574	0.556	0.561	0.565	0.293
Log-Likelihood	-32.319	-33.700	-33.301	-32.986	-69.709
AIC	0.488	0.506	0.501	0.497	0.977

Notes: Huber / White standard errors are reported in parenthesis for coefficient estimates to account for potential heteroskedasticity, where *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$ and * $p < 0.1$. The indicators $communication_t$, PR_t^{EC} and LM_t are all standardised. ME_3 denotes the marginal effect of a unit increase in each of the standardised indicators on the probability of an interest rate rise at the next policy meeting (other independent variables held at their sample average).

8. Discussion and Policy Insights

This study has examined the importance of the language in central bank communication. Our results clearly highlight that policymaker's description of the economic environment provides valuable insight into future policy decisions, improving the degree of predictability. In contrast to Ehrmann and Fratzscher (2007) who find BoE decisions to be less predictable than other central banks, we argue that the BoE policy decisions are reasonably predictable when considering all relevant information. We find that the information provided in the minutes complements different macroeconomic data releases. This supports the argument conveyed by

Andersson, Dillén and Sellin (2006), that central banks deviate from a standard Taylor rule as otherwise there would be no signal to extract from communication.

More broadly, this finding is consistent with the widely accepted phenomenon that greater transparency improves the predictability of monetary policy (Blinder et al., 2008). The implications of greater transparency are debated in the literature. Woodford (2005) argues that greater transparency can help to improve the effectiveness of monetary policy. On the other hand, Issing (2014) suggests that absolute transparency can increase the difficulty of the problem facing central bankers when unforeseen economic developments occur. Regardless, the publication of the minutes represents one method to increase the information conveyed to the public with regards to the central bank's operations, and this is valuable for predicting the future announcements.

The results reported in this dissertation have important policy implications for central banks. Firstly, we have outlined that readers are able to extract signals for subsequent meetings. This implies financial markets and members of the public can use this information to better predict interest rate changes as the language published aligns with future actions. Thus, central banks should consider the degree of accountability related to publishing minutes, whereby strong descriptive language may impact short-term expectations. Jung (2016) outlines that many central banks, such as the FED, continue to publish the meeting minutes with a substantial lag. Our results may suggest that the prompt release of minutes can help to reduce the degree of uncertainty around future policy action. Secondly, it highlights the importance of carefully choosing the specific words used in published communication. Assuming agents understand the importance of language, this descriptive avenue may play a key role in navigating policy. This is consistent with the argument of Bernanke, Reinhart and Sack (2004), that communication can be a useful monetary policy tool when nominal interest rates are constrained by the effective lower bound.

There are various limitations that must be considered with our results. There exists a degree of subjectivity in the construction of our indicator with the use of textual analysis and dictionaries. Whilst automated textual analysis depends less on subjective judgement than manually classifying documents (Apel & Grimaldi, 2012), there remains some judgment around the use of the dictionary. The words included in our dictionary may not be exhaustive, and further expansion of the dictionary may be warranted for further research. Moreover, all words in our dictionary are treated with equal weight, which may not capture the relative differences in importance amongst

words. For instance, the signal extracted may differ by topic and be state-dependent to the current economic environment. Words describing the dynamics of the labour market may carry greater weight when this is a driving factor of inflation. Whilst the methodology of Picault and Renault (2017) uses a term-weighted approach, when this is applied to BoE minutes in the robustness section, the results show this measure is less informative than our indicator. This highlights that the term-weighting may need to be tailored to the specific central bank.

Nonetheless, these findings pave the way for further analysis in the field of BoE communication. The techniques applied in our study could be used to examine a broader range of communication events including speeches or monetary policy reports, as well as extended to other central banks. In addition, our analysis did not analyse financial markets response to the release of the minutes. This would provide an avenue to assess the extent to which market participants value the words used by policymakers. This would be an interesting exercise as the BoE currently releases the minutes on the same day as the policy decision, which differs to many other central banks that release minutes with a lag. Therefore, disentangling the reaction to different information sources may further improve the understanding of monetary policy transmission.

9. Conclusion

Does the language used in central bank communication provide valuable information for future monetary policy? Using an ordered probit model, this study finds significant evidence communication can help to predict subsequent policy decisions alongside macroeconomic data releases. We construct a communication indicator for the BoE minutes using natural language processing techniques. Our indicator remains highly significant alongside an augmented Taylor rule and outperforms measures that are constructed by applying other methods to quantify BoE minutes. This highlights the importance of tailoring textual analysis to the idiosyncrasies of BoE communication. Furthermore, the robustness of the result when considering decisions that relate to unconventional monetary policy highlights the value of qualitative communication in different policy environment. This has implications for policymaker's when trying to understand the impact of communication and assessing the optimal degree of transparency. Moreover, these findings support the notion that the words selected by central bankers match their deeds.

Although, it is important to note that these findings relate to the application of our methodology to minutes without considering wider communication channels. Our

reproduceable method should be applied to other forms of communication in further studies to extract the degree of hawkishness conveyed by policymakers. Further examination of the impact of communication should be carried out, including the financial market reactions, to greater understand the broader implications for monetary policy transmission and the real economy effects. Nonetheless, this dissertation sheds light on the dynamics of quantifying central bank communication in the UK, an area that has been less explored relative to other advanced economies. It is evident that minutes provide an informative communication source to extract signals for what the future holds.

Bibliography

- Andersson, M., Dillén, H. and Sellin, P., 2006. Monetary policy signaling and movements in the term structure of interest rates. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 53(8), pp.1815–1855.
- Apel, M. and Grimaldi, M., 2012. *The Information Content of Central Bank Minutes*. Stockholm: Sveriges Riksbank Working Paper Series.
- Apel, M., Grimaldi, M. and Hull, I., 2022. How Much Information Do Monetary Policy Committees Disclose? Evidence from the FOMC's Minutes and Transcripts. *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking*, 54(5).
- Asteriou, D. and Hall, S.G., 2021. *Applied econometrics*. London: Macmillan.
- Bank of England (2012). *Minutes of the Monetary Policy Committee meeting 11 and 12 January 2012*. London: Bank of England.
- Bank of England (2013). *Minutes of the Monetary Policy Committee meeting 31 July and 1 August 2013*. London: Bank of England.
- Bank of England (2015). *Monetary policy summary and minutes of the Monetary Policy Committee meeting ending on 6 October 2015*. London: Bank of England.
- Bank of England, 2023a. *Market intelligence* [Online]. www.bankofengland.co.uk. Available from: <https://www.bankofengland.co.uk/markets/market-intelligence>.
- Bank of England, 2023b. *Monetary Policy Summary, February 2023* [Online]. www.bankofengland.co.uk. Bank of England. Available from: <https://www.bankofengland.co.uk/monetary-policy-summary-and-minutes/2023/february-2023>.
- Baranowski, P., Bennani, H. and Doryń, W., 2021. Do the ECB's introductory statements help predict monetary policy? Evidence from a tone analysis. *European Journal of Political Economy*, 66.
- Bennani, H., Fanta, N., Gertler, P. and Horvath, R., 2020. Does central bank communication signal future monetary policy in a (post)-crisis era? The case of the ECB. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 104.
- Bennani, H. and Neuenkirch, M., 2016. The (home) bias of European central bankers: new evidence based on speeches. *Applied Economics*, 49(11), pp.1114–1131.
- Bernanke, B., 2015. Inaugurating a new blog post [Online]. *Brookings*. Available from: <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/inaugurating-a-new-blog/>.
- Bernanke, B., Reinhart, V. and Sack, B., 2004. Monetary Policy Alternatives at the Zero Bound: An Empirical Assessment. *Finance and Economics Discussion Series*, 2004(48), pp.1–113.
- Bernanke, B.S. and Reinhart, V.R., 2004. Conducting Monetary Policy at Very Low Short-Term Interest Rates. *American Economic Review*, 94(2), pp.85–90.

- Blanchard, O., Cerutti, E. and Summers, L., 2015. Inflation and Activity - Two Explorations and their Monetary Policy Implications. *IMF Working Papers*, 15(230).
- Blattner, T., Catenaro, M., Ehrmann, M., Strauch, R. and Turunen, J., 2008. The predictability of monetary policy. Frankfurt: European Central Bank.
- Blei, D.M., Ng, A.Y. and Jordan, M.I., 2003. Latent Dirichlet Allocation. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 3, pp.993–1022.
- Blinder, A.S., 2008. *The Quiet Revolution*. New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Blinder, A.S., Ehrmann, M., Fratzscher, M., De Haan, J. and Jansen, D.-J., 2008. Central Bank Communication and Monetary Policy: A Survey of Theory and Evidence. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 46(4), pp.910–945.
- Bonciani, D. and Oh, J., 2023. Monetary Policy Inertia and the Paradox of Flexibility. *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*, 151.
- Brant, R., 1990. Assessing Proportionality in the Proportional Odds Model for Ordinal Logistic Regression. *Biometrics*, 46(4).
- Broadbent, B., 2017. *Brexit and interest rates*. London School of Economics.
- Brooks, C., 2019. *Introductory Econometrics for Finance*. 4th ed. Cambridge, United Kingdom; New York, Ny: Cambridge University Press.
- Cao, J., Xia, T., Li, J., Zhang, Y. and Tang, S., 2009. A density-based method for adaptive LDA model selection. *Neurocomputing*, 72(7), pp.1775–1781.
- Chang, J., Boyd-Graber, J., Gerrish, S., Wang, C. and Blei, D.M., 2009. Reading Tea Leaves: How Humans Interpret Topic Models. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*.
- Cobham, D., 2003. Why does the Monetary Policy Committee smooth interest rates? *Oxford Economic Papers*, 55(3), pp.467–493.
- Connolly, E. and Kohler, M., 2004. *News and Interest Rate Expectations: A Study of Six Central Banks*. Sydney: Reserve Bank of Australia.
- Coppel, J. and Connolly, E., 2003. What Do Financial Market Data Tell Us about Monetary Policy Transparency. *RePEc: Research Papers in Economics*.
- Daykin, A.R. and Moffatt, P.G., 2002. Analyzing Ordered Responses: A Review of the Ordered Probit Model. *Understanding Statistics*, 1(3), pp.157–166.
- De Jong, R.M. and Sakarya, N., 2016. The Econometrics of the Hodrick-Prescott Filter. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 98(2), pp.310–317.
- Deveaud, R., Sanjuan, E. and Bellot, P. (2014). Accurate and effective latent concept modelling for ad hoc information retrieval. *Document Numérique*, 17(1), pp.61–84.
- Dow, S., Klaes, M. and Montagnoli, A., 2009. Risk and uncertainty in central bank signals: an analysis of monetary policy committee minutes. *Metroeconomica*, 60(4), pp.584–618.

- Ehrmann, M. and Fratzscher, M., 2007. Communication by Central Bank Committee Members: Different Strategies, Same Effectiveness? *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking*, 39(2-3), pp.509–541.
- El-Shagi, M. and Jung, A., 2015. Have minutes helped markets to predict the MPC's monetary policy decisions? *European Journal of Political Economy*, 39, pp.222–234.
- Froemel, M., Joyce, M. and Kaminska, I., 2022. *The local supply channel of QE: evidence from the Bank of England's gilt purchases* [Online]. London: Bank of England. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4130492>.
- Gardner, B., Scotti, C. and Vega, C., 2021. Words speak as loudly as actions: Central bank communication and the response of equity prices to macroeconomic announcements. *Journal of Econometrics*, 231(2).
- Gerlach-Kristen, P., 2004. Is the MPC's Voting Record Informative about Future UK Monetary Policy? *Scandinavian Journal of Economics*, 106(2), pp.299–313.
- Greene, W.H., 2020. *Econometric Analysis*. 8th ed. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.
- Hansen, S. and McMahon, M., 2016. Shocking language: Understanding the macroeconomic effects of central bank communication. *Journal of International Economics*, 99(1).
- Hansen, S., McMahon, M. and Prat, A., 2017. Transparency and Deliberation Within the FOMC: A Computational Linguistics Approach. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 133(2), pp.801–870.
- Hansen, S., McMahon, M. and Tong, M., 2019. The long-run information effect of central bank communication. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 108, pp.185–202.
- Haskel, J., 2024. *Implications of current wage inflation*. Kings College London.
- Hayo, B. and Neuenkirch, M., 2010. Do Federal Reserve communications help predict federal funds target rate decisions? *Journal of Macroeconomics*, 32(4), pp.1014–1024.
- Hayo, B. and Neuenkirch, M., 2015. Central bank communication in the financial crisis: Evidence from a survey of financial market participants. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 59, pp.166–181.
- Hodrick, R.J. and Prescott, E.C., 1997. Postwar U.S. Business Cycles: An Empirical Investigation. *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking*, 29(1).
- Hubert, P. and Labondance, F., 2021. The signaling effects of central bank tone. *European Economic Review*, 133, p.103684.
- Issing, O., 2014. Communication and transparency – The example of the ECB. *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*, 49, pp.70–73.
- Jansen, D.-J. and De Haan, J., 2009. Has ECB communication been helpful in predicting interest rate decisions? An evaluation of the early years of the Economic and Monetary Union. *Applied Economics*, 41(16), pp.1995–2003.

- Jung, A., 2016. Have minutes helped to predict fed funds rate changes? *Journal of Macroeconomics*, 49, pp.18–32.
- Kohn, D.L. and Sack, B., 2003. Central Bank Talk: Does It Matter and Why? *Finance and Economics Discussion Series*, 2003(55), pp.1–37.
- Kuttner, K. and Robinson, T., 2010. Understanding the flattening Phillips curve. *The North American Journal of Economics and Finance*, 21(2), pp.110–125.
- Liu, A., He, H., Tu, X.M. and Tang, W., 2023. On testing proportional odds assumptions for proportional odds models. *General Psychiatry*, 36(3).
- Loughran, T. and McDonald, B., 2011. When Is a Liability Not a Liability? Textual Analysis, Dictionaries, and 10-Ks. *The Journal of Finance*, 66(1), pp.35–65.
- Lucca, D.O. and Trebbi, F., 2009. *Measuring central bank communication: an automated approach with application to FOMC statements*. Cambridge: National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Orphanides, A., 2001. Monetary Policy Rules Based on Real-Time Data. *American Economic Review*, 91(4), pp.964–985.
- Picault, M. and Renault, T., 2017. Words are not all created equal: A new measure of ECB communication. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 79, pp.136–156.
- Porter, M.F., 1980. An algorithm for suffix stripping [Online]. *Program*, 14(3), pp.130–137. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb046814>.
- Ramsden, D., 2023. *Quantitative tightening: the story so far*. London.
- Reeves, R. and Sawicki, M., 2007. Do financial markets react to Bank of England communication? *European Journal of Political Economy*, 23(1), pp.207–227.
- Regenwetter, M. and Davis-Stober, C.P., 2017. The Role of Independence and Stationarity in Probabilistic Models of Binary Choice. *Journal of Behavioral Decision Making*, 31(1), pp.100–114.
- Romer, C.D. and Romer, D.H., 1989. Does Monetary Policy Matter? A New Test in the Spirit of Friedman and Schwartz. *NBER Macroeconomics Annual*, 4, pp.121–170.
- Rosa, C., 2011. Words that shake traders: The stock market's reaction to central bank communication in real time. *Journal of Empirical Finance*, 18(5), pp.915–934.
- Rosa, C. and Verga, G., 2007. On the consistency and effectiveness of central bank communication: Evidence from the ECB. *European Journal of Political Economy*, 23(1), pp.146–175.
- Sauer, S. and Sturm, J.-E., 2007. Using Taylor Rules to Understand European Central Bank Monetary Policy. *German Economic Review*, 8(3), pp.375–398.
- Schnabel, I., 2023. *Disinflation and the Phillips Curve*. Frankfurt.
- Sturm, J.-E. and De Haan, J., 2010. Does central bank communication really lead to better forecasts of policy decisions? New evidence based on a Taylor rule model for the ECB. *Review of World Economics*, 147(1), pp.41–58.

Tadle, R.C., 2021. FOMC minutes sentiments and their impact on financial markets. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 118, p.106021.

Taylor, J.B., 1993. Discretion versus policy rules in practice. *Carnegie-Rochester Conference Series on Public Policy*, 39, pp.195–214.

Vanderhart, P.G., 2000. The Federal Reserve's reaction function under Greenspan: An ordinal probit analysis. *Journal of Macroeconomics*, 22(4).

Wecken, G.W. and Büchsenmann, T.V., 2019. *How Closely do Financial Markets Really Listen to Central Bank Tone? A High-frequency Study on ECB Press Conferences*. Master Thesis. Copenhagen Business School.

Woodford, M., 2005. *Central Bank Communication and Policy Effectiveness*. National Bureau of Economic Research.

Appendix

A1: Dictionary

Term	Hawkish modifier	Dovish modifier
Growth	accelerate buoyant edge up expand increase high pick-up pickup rise rose step up strength strong upside	contract curtail decelerate decline decrease downside drop fall fell low moderate slow sluggish weak disappoint
Inflation	accelerate boost elevate escalate high higher increase jump pickup pick-up rise rose rising risen run-up runup strong surge up upward build emerge great greater height intensify mount stoke upside firm firmer sustain	decelerate decline decrease down downward drop fall fallen fell low lower mute reduce slow stable subdued soft softer subside weak weaker contained abate dampen diminish ease low moderate recede temper downside
Labour market and wage growth	strained tight increase rise	ease loosen soft weak

	<p>rose high elevate strong strength pickup pick-up fast faster</p>	<p>decrease fell fall reduce mute subdued slow slower</p>
Employment	<p>expand gain improve increase pick-up pickup raise rise rose strength turn-up</p>	<p>slow decline reduce weak deteriorate shrink shrank fall fell drop contract sluggish</p>
Unemployment	<p>decline fall fell low reduce</p>	<p>elevate high increase rise rose</p>
Household demand	<p>accelerate buoyant edge up expand increase high pick-up pickup rise rose step up strength strong upside</p>	<p>contract curtail decelerate decline decrease downside drop fall fell low moderate slow sluggish weak disappoint</p>

A2: Examples of sentence classification

Example 1 – Topic 1

*The preliminary release suggested that GDP has **increased** by 0.6% in Q2, in line with the Committee's expectation.*

→ **Hawkish modifier 'increased'.**

Source: Bank of England (2013)

Example 2 - Topic 4

*Also in line with the pre-release arrangements, the Governor informed the Committee that producer input prices had **decreased** by 0.6% in December, reflecting lower prices of crude oil, imported chemicals and imported parts and equipment.*

→ **Dovish modifier 'decreased'.**

Source: Bank of England (2012)

Example 3 – Topic 7

Taking this into account implied annual growth in unit labour costs of around 1.8%.

→ **There are no modifiers included.**

Source: Bank of England (2015)

A3: Financial market data sensitivity

Dependent Variable: Forward interest rate swap 1y1y

Model Variables	Period: 2016-2023					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
<i>CPI YoY</i>	4.244*** (1.195)					
<i>Core CPI YoY</i>		4.832*** (1.068)				
<i>Unemployment ILO</i>			0.610 (0.437)			
<i>Average weekly earnings</i>				2.073*** (0.778)		
<i>Mortgage approvals</i>					-0.425 (0.512)	
<i>Industrial production</i>						-0.772 (0.453)
<i>Constant</i>	-0.330 (0.804)	-0.330 (0.769)	2.02*** (0.635)	1.969*** (0.597)	-0.993 (0.610)	0.347 (0.674)
<i>Observations</i>	94	94	93	94	94	94
<i>R²</i>	0.227	0.294	0.010	0.113	0.005	0.014

Note: Newey-west robust standard errors are utilised and reported in parenthesis. Significance levels are indicated with *** significant at 1%, ** significant at 5% and * significant at 10%. The model regresses the daily change in the 1y1y OIS swap on the surprise component of each data release. The surprise is calculated as the difference between the realised data outturn and the prior expectation from the Reuters poll.

A4: Policy decision for different values of our communication indicator

A5: Summary statistics

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	Max	ADF t- statistic
$communication_t$	0.000	0.316	-0.905	0.739	-4.55
$\Delta(\pi_t - \pi_t^*)$	-0.018	0.447	-2.1	2	-5.03
$\Delta(y_t - y_t^*)$	0.017	3.702	-21.627	30.849	-12.53

Notes: The ADF test has the null hypothesis that there exists a unit root. In all cases we can reject the null at the 1% significance level, highlighted by the t-statistics being in bold.

A6: Ordered logit model

		Policy decision (Δi_{t+1})		
		(1)	(2)	(3)
Δi_t		5.204*** (0.752)	4.893*** (0.788)	4.932*** (0.790)
$\Delta(\pi_t - \pi_t^*)$		1.547** (0.645)	1.442** (0.585)	1.473** (0.583)
$\Delta(y_t - y_t^*)$		-0.042 (0.035)		-0.045 (0.037)
$communication_t$			2.863*** (0.900)	2.875*** (0.890)
Cut-off coefficients				
δ_1		5.660*** (1.117)	4.361*** (1.217)	4.465*** (1.232)
δ_2		14.150*** (1.830)	13.824*** (1.942)	13.906*** (1.945)
Marginal effects				
ME_3			0.114* (0.063)	0.114* (0.063)
Observations		153	153	153
Pseudo R ²		0.550	0.579	0.581
Log-Likelihood		-34.164	-31.931	-31.782
AIC		0.512	0.483	0.494

Notes: Huber-White standard errors are reported in parenthesis to account for potential

heteroskedasticity, where *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$ and * $p < 0.1$. The coefficients are in log-odds form.

ME_3 denotes the marginal effect of a unit increase in the communication indicator on the probability of an interest rate rise at the next policy meeting (other independent variables held at their sample average).

A7: QE announcements

Date	Announcement
5 March 2009	The MPC announces it will purchase £75 billion of assets over 3 months funded by the issue of central bank money.
7 May 2009	The MPC announces that QE asset purchases will be extended by £50 billion to £125 billion.
6 August 2009	The MPC announces that QE asset purchases will be extended by £50 billion to £175 billion.
5 November 2009	The MPC announces that QE asset purchases will be extended by £25 billion to £200 billion.
4 February 2010	The MPC announces that QE asset purchases will be maintained at £200 billion.
6 October 2011	The MPC announces that QE asset purchases will be extended by £75 billion to £275 billion.
9 February 2012	The MPC announces that QE asset purchases will be extended by £50 billion to £325 billion.
10 May 2012	The MPC announces that QE asset purchases will be maintained at £325 billion.
5 July 2012	The MPC announces that the QE asset purchases will be extended by £50 billion to £375 billion.
4 August 2016	The MPC announces an expansion of the asset purchase scheme for UK government bonds of £60 billion, taking the total stock of these asset purchases to £435 billion.
19 March 2020	The MPC announced it the decision to expand its QE programme by £200 billion.
18 June 2020	The MPC made a further decision expand its QE by a further £100 billion, while slowing the pace of purchases.
5 November 2020	The MPC decided to further expand the stock of purchases by £150 billion, taking the target QE stock of gilt holdings to £875 billion.

Source: Froemel, Joyce and Kaminska (2022)